

DYNAMICS OF SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF 11-13-YEAR-OLD KARATE WKF BOYS PRACTICING AT THE INITIAL TRAINING STAGE

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Abstract: In this article, the effectiveness of special exercises aimed at the development of special physical training and technical-tactical training of 11-13-year-old karate athletes practicing in specialized sports schools was studied on the basis of pedagogical experience.

Keywords: physical fitness, physical qualities, technical and tactical training, physical development.

ДИНАМИКА СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ МАЛЬЧИКОВ ВКФ КАРАТЭ 11-13 ЛЕТ, ЗАНИМАЮЩИХСЯ НА НАЧАЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ

Аннотация: В данной статье на основе педагогического опыта изучена эффективность специальных упражнений, направленных на развитие специальной физической подготовки и технико-тактической подготовки каратистов 11-13 лет, занимающихся в специализированных спортивных школах.

Ключевые слова: физическая подготовленность, физические качества, технико-тактическая подготовка, физическое развитие.

IMPORTANCE

At the present time, the high level of attention paid to karate (WKF) sport on a global scale and the fact that this sport has become popular on a global scale indicates how high-level sport karate is.

Many scientists have conducted their research in order to improve the level of physical fitness of young karate players practicing this type of sport and to eliminate their mistakes and shortcomings. Including Galochkin G.P., Yefremov A.K., Sannikov V.A. and many other experts emphasized the need to pay serious attention to the development of physical qualities and physical abilities of young athletes from the age of the initial training stage. Indicators of physical fitness of athletes who are constantly practicing karate, technical and tactical training, training place, conditions, individual cases of athletes and the trainer can be in different forms depending on the training methods.

The level of physical fitness of young athletes practicing karate and correctly interpreted tasks are of great importance for achieving high results. One of the main goals of our research is to determine the general classification of the results obtained during this research and to identify and evaluate the aspects that are formed through the technical and tactical skills of young athletes.

Wide opportunities created by the president of our country and sports schools for children and teenagers designed to train highly qualified athletes, sports schools of higher skill, Olympic Reserve Colleges, the number of specialized schools allows young people to train in certain types of sports even in remote areas. This research practice was conducted to determine to what extent the physical fitness indicators of 11-13-year-old athletes who are practicing karate using the wide opportunities provided are being formed.

However, until now, the technical and tactical training of 11-13 year old karate players, the intensity of the use of tools aimed at the direction of physical quality indicators and the issues of

determining size standards remain insufficiently studied. This situation makes the topic of this study relevant.

THE PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

To study the development indicators of the dynamics of special physical fitness of 11-13-year-old karate players engaged in the initial training stage.

TASKS OF RESEARCH

- Determining the development dynamics of physical fitness indicators of 11-year-old karate players.
- Determining the development dynamics of physical fitness indicators of 13-year-old karate players.

The object of research: training process of 11-13-year-old karate players in the initial training stage.

The subject of research: researching the dynamics of special physical training of 11-13-year-old karate players engaged in the initial training stage.

Research methods: analysis of scientific and methodical literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, mathematical and statistical analysis.

Organization of research: In research, Young karate players (n=80) participating in the training group at Chirchik city sports school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE CONDUCTED RESEARCH

Nowadays, the training processes of many highly qualified karate coaches with young athletes have brought high results and raised the honor of our country to higher levels, many of our scientists, with their research on this type of sport, are helping to identify the correct distribution of physical loads given to athletes during the training processes of young people and to eliminate the mistakes of young athletes.

The indicators of the development of specific physical fitness levels were determined through each specified control test.

Practical observational tests were conducted to determine to what extent the dynamics of physical development indicators of 11-year-old karate players are taking shape during training. The first selected practical control test was evaluated using the Kixon technique, and special physical quality indicators of karate players were determined. Accordingly, the results of 11-year-old karate boys at the beginning of the year were equal to 10 ± 1.7 , and the coefficient of variation was ($V=2.23\%$). By the end of the year, the results of these indicators for young karate players were found to be equal to 15 ± 1.4 , and the variation was ($V=2.12\%$). The difference between the beginning of the year and the end of the year was 4.97. However, statistically significant differences were found when comparing the obtained results ($p>0.05$).

Table 1. Dynamics of special physical training of 11-year-old karate players

Norms	TO		TK		Difference	t	P
	X±α	V%	X±α	V%			
Kihon (technique for performing methods)	<u>10±1.7</u>	<u>2.23</u>	<u>15±1.4</u>	<u>2.12</u>	<u>1.97</u>	<u>1.92</u>	<u>>0.05</u>
Performing a kata (A summary of methods and techniques)	<u>14±1.1</u>	<u>2.09</u>	<u>18±0.71</u>	<u>2.23</u>	<u>1.96</u>	<u>1.24</u>	<u>>0.05</u>

Kumite (Discussion of fighting methods)	<u>12±1.9</u>	<u>2.04</u>	<u>20±1.41</u>	<u>2.09</u>	<u>7.95</u>	<u>1.98</u>	<u>>0.05</u>
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13-year-old karate players were also given this control test exercise. According to this, it was found that their results at the beginning of the year were 14±1.7, and by the end of the year their results improved to 18±1.2. The coefficient of variation was (V=2.04%) at the beginning of the year, and it was equal to (V=2.08%) by the end of the year. The difference between pre-experiment and post-experiment results was 3.95. Statistically reliable differences were found when comparing the obtained results (p>0.05).

In order to determine the level of special physical fitness of 11-year-old karate athletes, the next control exercise was the exercise of performing a set of Kata techniques. young karate players returned 14±1.1 results at the beginning of the year, the coefficient of variation was (V=9.02%). By the end of the year, these indicators were equal to 18±0.71, the coefficient of variation (V=1.96%). The statistical difference between the beginning of the year and the end of the year was equal to 3.96.

13-year-old karate players were also subjected to control tests using the exercise of performing a collection of Kata techniques. The indicators of 13-year-old karate players at the beginning of the year were found to be equal to 16±1.1. it is possible to see that by the end of the year these indicators have improved to 20±0.71. The coefficient of variation was at the beginning of the year (V=2.01%), but at the end of the year it was hidden (V=2.05%). there were no statistical differences between them (p>0.05). (See Table 2).

Table 2. Dynamics of special physical fitness index of 13-year-old karate players

Norms	TO		TK		Difference	t	P
	X±α	V%	X±α	V%			
Kihon (technique for performing methods)	<u>14±1.7</u>	<u>2.04</u>	<u>18±1.2</u>	<u>2.08</u>	<u>1.83</u>	<u>1.72</u>	<u>>0.05</u>
Performing a kata (A summary of methods and techniques)	<u>16±1.1</u>	<u>2.01</u>	<u>20±0.71</u>	<u>2.05</u>	<u>1.78</u>	<u>1.21</u>	<u>>0.05</u>
Kumite (Discussion of fighting methods)	<u>14±1.9</u>	<u>2.03</u>	<u>20±1.41</u>	<u>2.09</u>	<u>1.90</u>	<u>1.91</u>	<u>>0.05</u>

The results of quickness of 11-year-old karate boys were determined through the exercise of Kumite fighting techniques. The indicators at the beginning of the year returned a result of 12±1.9. The coefficient of variation was (V=2.04%). By the end of the year, they received 20±1.41. The statistical difference between them was found to be equal to 7.95. Statistical differences are valid (t=1.98 p>0.05). (See Figure 1).

Special physical training indicators of 13-year-old karate boys were determined using Kumite fighting methods. The results of karate players at the beginning of the year were 14±1.9, and by the end of the year this index reached 20±1.41. At the beginning of the year, the coefficient of variation was (V=2.03%), at the end of the year (V=2.09%). The statistical difference between

them was found to be equal to 2.09. Statistical differences are valid ($t=1.16$ $p>0.05$). (See Table 2)

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of scientific-methodological and special literature, pedagogical observations, pedagogical control, instrumental methodology and the results of pedagogical experience, the following conclusions were reached.

In the training system of karate players, many research studies were conducted to control and evaluate their special movement training. Pedagogical test sets have been created to control the strength, speed-strength, endurance, agility, speed-strength, power endurance and other movement readiness of young karate players and their effectiveness has been proven in pedagogical experience. However, not enough scientific research has been conducted to determine the speed, accuracy, impact force, working capacity and other parameters of the karate athletes' special physical training and physical indicators. At present, the use of innovative technologies in the system of training athletes and their application to the training process has become an integral part of the system.

In order to determine the physical development indicators and physical qualities of 11-13-year-old karate players who are practicing at the initial training stage, control test exercises were taken from them. In the pedagogical experiment, indicators of speed and physical quality of karate players of both ages were determined. According to the results of this control test, the results of the quickness of 11-year-old karate boys were determined through the exercise of Kumite fighting methods. The indicators at the beginning of the year returned a result of 12 ± 1.9 . The coefficient of variation was ($V=2.04\%$). By the end of the year, they received 20 ± 1.41 . The statistical difference between them was found to be equal to 7.95. Statistical differences are valid ($t=1.98$ $p>0.05$). Special physical training indicators of 13-year-old karate boys were determined using Kumite fighting methods. the results of karate players at the beginning of the year showed 14 ± 1.9 results, and by the end of the year this index reached 20 ± 1.41 . The coefficient of variation at the beginning of the year was ($V=2.03\%$), at the end of the year ($V=2.09\%$). The statistical difference between them was found to be equal to 2.09. Statistical differences are valid ($t=1.16$ $p>0.05$).

Necessary recommendations and instructions were developed in order to eliminate the identified shortcomings. The levels of special physical fitness of 11-13-year-old karate players who are engaged in the initial training stage were properly organized during the control test practice.

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